

An Open-Data Pipeline for Measuring Occupational AI Vulnerability: A Replication of Manning and Aguirre (2026)

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Abstract

This paper replicates Manning and Aguirre’s (2026) occupation-level analysis of workers’ vulnerability to AI-induced displacement. It imports the same published AI-exposure scores, reconstructs the adaptive-capacity index, and replaces the original study’s proprietary Lightcast geographic input with public OEWS area employment and Census Gazetteer land-area data. The replication retains 388 occupations covering 147.4 million workers (95.6% of the OEWS employment universe), compared with 356 occupations covering 147.9 million workers (95.9%) in the original study. The employment-weighted correlation between AI exposure and adaptive capacity is 0.474, compared with the original estimate of 0.502. The replicated vulnerable group contains 6.0 million workers (4.1% of covered employment), compared with 6.1 million (4.2%) in the original, and remains concentrated in clerical and administrative occupations. The public geographic-density measure has a correlation of 0.417 with AI exposure, compared with 0.426 for the proprietary measure. The close agreement across these estimates confirms Manning and Aguirre’s principal findings and shows that they hold even when using only public data.

Keywords: artificial intelligence; labor displacement; adaptive capacity; occupational exposure; replication; open data

JEL classification: J23; J24; J62; O33; C81

Data Availability: The Python code and data to reproduce the results of this replication are openly available on Zenodo (DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.20534294](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20534294)).

Conflict of Interest: The author declares no conflicts of interest.

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1 Introduction

A growing literature measures how strongly occupations are exposed to AI by matching technological capabilities to occupational tasks (Brynjolfsson et al., 2018; Webb, 2020; Felten et al., 2023; Eloundou et al., 2024a; Hampole et al., 2025), building on the task-based framework of Autor et al. (2003) and Acemoglu and Autor (2011). AI exposure does not, however, predict how costly a transition would be if displacement occurs. Those costs depend on factors shaping a worker’s ability to adjust, including liquid financial buffers, transferable skills, access to a dense labor market, and age-related barriers to reemployment (Chetty, 2008; Nawakitphaitoon and Ormiston, 2016; Bleakley and Lin, 2012; Eggenberger et al., 2022; Athey et al., 2024).

Manning and Aguirre (2026) (hereafter MA) are one of the first to quantify this distinction for the U.S. workforce as a whole. They pair occupational AI exposure with an occupation-level adaptive-capacity index and define *vulnerable workers* as those in occupations that simultaneously rank in the top quartile of AI exposure and the bottom quartile of adaptive capacity—a group facing the greatest displacement risk with the fewest resources to absorb it. MA find that AI exposure and adaptive capacity are positively correlated, while this vulnerable group is relatively small and concentrated in clerical and administrative work. The distinction between exposure and vulnerability bears directly on how transition assistance is targeted, which makes the reliability of MA’s estimates worth establishing independently.

This paper replicates MA’s analysis using public data, testing both whether their published estimates can be recovered without their code and whether their proprietary geographic input is necessary. MA use Lightcast employment by county and metropolitan area to measure the labor-market density surrounding each occupation’s workers. This replication replaces that input with public OEWS employment for core-based statistical area (CBSA) and nonmetropolitan reporting areas (U.S. Bureau of Labor Statistics, 2024b), and computes land area from the Census 2024 CBSA and county Gazetteer files (U.S. Census Bureau, 2024d).

The replication confirms MA’s main empirical patterns, and Table 1 summarizes the comparison. The final public-data sample—hereafter the *final sample*—of 388 occupations covering 147.4 million workers (95.6% of the OEWS universe) compares with 356 occupations covering 147.9 million workers (95.9%) in MA. The employment-weighted correlation between AI exposure and adaptive

capacity is 0.474, compared with MA’s 0.502. Of 37.3 million workers in the top quartile of AI exposure, 27.9 million work in occupations with above-median adaptive capacity, compared with 26.5 million of 37.1 million in MA. Nine vulnerable occupations employ 6.0 million workers, compared with 6.1 million in MA’s corresponding group.

Table 1: Results Summary

Quantity	MA	Replication
Final sample, occupations	356	388
Workforce coverage	95.9% (147.9M)	95.6% (147.4M)
r (AI exposure, adaptive capacity)	0.502	0.474
Workers in top quartile of AI exposure	37.1M	37.3M
with above-median adaptive capacity	26.5M	27.9M
Vulnerable workers	6.1M (4.2%)	6.0M (4.1%)
Vulnerable occupations	10	9
r (AI exposure, geographic density)	0.426	0.417

Notes: M denotes millions of workers and r the employment-weighted correlation. MA entries are from Manning and Aguirre (2026), Tables 4, 7, and 11 and the accompanying text.

Certain components required interpretation because MA do not specify the implementation in enough detail to recover every coding choice, especially the filters used to construct occupation-level SIPP estimates. Separately, this replication uses O*NET 30.3 rather than O*NET 30.1 because O*NET’s file structure was reorganized in 30.3, and building against the newer structure keeps the pipeline compatible with the likely format of future O*NET releases.

The paper is organized as follows: Section 2 describes the data replication and identifies all methodological departures from the original. Section 3 reports the replicated distributions and compares the main estimates. Section 4 subjects the replication to systematic robustness checks and validates the public geographic measure. Section 5 concludes. All statistics are employment-weighted unless otherwise stated.

2 Data and Replication Design

The dataset replication follows the same conceptual design as MA. Table 2 summarizes which inputs are unchanged, reproduced, refreshed, modified, or replaced.

Table 2: Data Sources and Departures from Manning and Aguirre (2026)

Component	MA input	Replication input	Departure
AI exposure	Eloundou et al. β	Eloundou et al. β	Unchanged
Age structure	ACS 2024	ACS 2024	Reproduced
Employment weights	OEWS May 2024	OEWS May 2024	Reproduced
Projected growth	BLS 2024–2034	BLS 2024–2034	Reproduced
Skill profiles	O*NET 30.1	O*NET 30.3	Refreshed
Net liquid wealth	SIPP 2022–2024	SIPP 2022–2024	Modified
Geographic density	Lightcast 2023	OEWS May 2024; Census Gaz. 2024	Replaced

Notes: “Reproduced” means the same source and method; “Refreshed” a newer version of the same source; “Modified” a methodological departure using the same source; and “Replaced” a public substitute for the original proprietary input. β is the composite exposure measure $E1 + 0.5 \times E2$ of [Eloundou et al. \(2024a\)](#), imported from the occupation-level scores in their public repository ([Eloundou et al., 2024b](#)).

2.1 Occupational Crosswalk and Sample Construction

The source data use three occupational taxonomies. SIPP and ACS use PUMS OCC codes, OEWS and BLS Employment Projections use SOC codes, and O*NET and the [Eloundou et al. \(2024a\)](#) exposure scores use O*NET-SOC codes. All sources are mapped to a Modified SIPP spine through PUMS OCC codes as a common intermediate:

$$\text{O*NET-SOC} \longrightarrow \text{SOC} \longrightarrow \text{PUMS OCC} \longrightarrow \text{Modified SIPP}.$$

The SOC-to-PUMS OCC step follows the Census Bureau’s published occupation code list ([U.S. Census Bureau, n.d.](#)). Where several detailed codes aggregate to one spine category, the aggregation weights use May 2024 OEWS national employment ([U.S. Bureau of Labor Statistics, 2024b](#)), falling back to the May 2016 release ([U.S. Bureau of Labor Statistics, 2016](#)) for detailed-SOC-code employments no longer published in 2024.

The Modified SIPP occupation list differs from the PUMS OCC translation only in three cases, each aligning a group of PUMS codes with the corresponding aggregated OEWS category ([Hopson, 2021](#)). PUMS OCC codes 0510, 0520, and 0530 are consolidated into 05MM (buyers and purchasing agents); codes 2001 and 2004 are consolidated into 200M (counselors); and codes 3601 and 3602 are consolidated into 36MM (home health and personal care aides).

An occupation enters the final sample only if it satisfies six criteria: national OEWS employment is available; the occupation has at least 15 pooled SIPP person-year observations; a skill profile is complete or imputed; ACS age data are present; an OEWS-based geographic density is defined;

and an [Eloundou et al. \(2024a\)](#) exposure score exists. Table 3 reports cumulative coverage through each criterion.

Table 3: Cumulative Sample Construction by Filtering Stage

Stage	MA		Replication	
	Occ.	Coverage	Occ.	Coverage
Full O*NET/OEWS universe	831	100.0%	831	100.00%
SOC to Modified SIPP mapping	523	100.0%	520	100.00%
Require ≥ 15 SIPP observations	369	97.2%	401	96.96%
Require non-missing wealth median	369	97.2%	401	96.96%
Require skill transferability	367	97.2%	401	96.96%
Require ACS age data	—	—	401	96.96%
Require OEWS geographic density	—	—	401	96.96%
Require AI exposure score	356	95.9%	388	95.62%

Notes: Filters are applied cumulatively. Coverage is the share of total May 2024 OEWS employment (154.19 million workers; [U.S. Bureau of Labor Statistics, 2024b](#)) accounted for by the retained occupations. MA values are from [Manning and Aguirre \(2026\)](#), Table 4; dashes mark stages MA do not report separately. The mapping-stage counts differ by universe, not by mapping: MA count the full SIPP classification of 523 categories, while the replication counts the 520 Modified SIPP categories reachable from OEWS. The three additional codes—9920 (unemployed or never worked), 9840 (military), and 6115 (fishing and hunting workers)—have no OEWS counterpart, so they carry no OEWS employment and leave coverage unchanged at every stage in which they appear. Each exits MA’s pipeline where the public data dictate: 9920 never appears in the 2022–2024 SIPP job records and cannot meet the observation threshold, while 9840 and 6115 hold ample SIPP observations but no OEWS code through which MA’s O*NET-to-OEWS chain can assign a skill profile, consistent with the two occupations MA shed at the skill stage without any change in coverage. Net of the three codes, MA’s counts are 520, 367, 367, 367, and 356, and the divergence from the replication arises entirely at the SIPP observation filter.

Two implementation choices determine which person-years contribute to the SIPP wealth estimates: whether the ≥ 15 SIPP observation threshold is applied to pooled person-years or to unique persons, and which monthly record supplies wealth and the final person weight. Table 4 reports the sample under each alternative.

Observation unit. The baseline applies the ≥ 15 threshold to pooled person-year observations, rather than to unique persons as in MA. The justification is grounded in the structure of the final person weight and the longitudinal design of SIPP. Exploratory data analysis of the raw SIPP files confirms that the final person weight varies across reference months within the same person-year; by extension it also differs across reference years for respondents observed in multiple waves. This matters because SIPP re-interviews the same households annually ([U.S. Census Bureau, 2024c](#)): 60% of 2022 respondents reappear in 2023, 52% of 2023 respondents reappear in 2024, and 30% appear in all three waves. In total, 40.8% of the 118,248 pooled person-years are repeat appearances.

Each repeat appearance carries its own final person weight, reflecting the composition of active survey respondents at a different point in time, and its own independently measured wealth. These are not duplicate observations. Collapsing to unique persons forces a choice between keeping only one year’s weight—discarding valid observations with independently issued weights—or combining weights that reflect different respondent compositions, which the survey design does not support. Either option corrupts the weight structure of the pooled file. The person-year is therefore the natural unit, as it is the level at which the final person weight is defined.

Wealth and the final person weight are drawn from the last observed month within the reference year regardless of which observation unit is used. After the ≥ 15 -observation SIPP filter, person-years yield 401 occupations and unique persons yield 386, the latter covering 148.7 million workers against the 149.9 million MA report. Because this difference is wholly within the SIPP wealth extraction stage, it isolates the counting rule from all other pipeline choices. Yet even under MA’s own unique-person rule the replication retains 386 occupations, not the 369 MA report (367 net of codes 9840 and 6115, which carry no OEWS employment; Table 3). Fewer occupations covering more workers cannot arise from a stricter observation threshold, which could only drop occupations and lower coverage together. This implies a difference in the underlying SIPP extraction. Because MA do not document that extraction in enough detail, its source cannot be identified and remains unresolved.

Snapshot month. For each person-year, the baseline extracts wealth and the final person weight from the last month that respondent was observed *within that reference year*. The counting-unit comparison above holds this snapshot rule fixed; this paragraph examines what happens when the snapshot rule itself is varied. Across the pooled 2022–2024 SIPP file, 118,248 person-years are observed. Of these, 772 (0.65%) are late joiners whose first observed month is after January and who would be lost under a January-only rule; 2,011 (1.70%) are early attritors whose last observed month is before December and who would be lost under a December-only rule. Adopting either fixed-calendar rule would discard person-years unnecessarily; accordingly, the replication uses the last-observed-month rule to retain all 118,248 person-years.

Table 4: Sensitivity of Sample Coverage to SIPP Observation Unit and Snapshot Month

Specification	Occupations	Employment coverage
<i>Observation unit for ≥ 15 threshold (snapshot: last observed)</i>		
Person-years (baseline)	401	97.0%
Unique persons	386	96.4%
<i>Manning and Aguirre</i>		
Unique persons	369	97.2%
<i>Wealth snapshot month (observation unit: person-years)</i>		
Last observed month (baseline)	401	97.0%
January only	401	97.0%
December only	399	96.9%

Notes: Each panel varies one dimension, holding the other at its baseline. All values are measured immediately after the ≥ 15 SIPP filter; coverage is relative to total May 2024 OEWS employment (154.19 million workers; U.S. Bureau of Labor Statistics, 2024b).

2.2 Construction of the Adaptive-Capacity Components

Adaptive capacity operationalizes four channels through which workers’ ability to absorb AI-induced displacement varies: financial resources to sustain job search (Chetty, 2008), skill portability to alternative work (Nawakitphaitoon and Ormiston, 2016; Eggenberger et al., 2022), local labor market density (Bleakley and Lin, 2012; Moretti and Yi, 2024), and age-related reemployment barriers (Couch and Placzek, 2010; Farber, 2017). Three components—wealth, transferability, and age—use MA’s underlying data. Geographic density replaces MA’s proprietary Lightcast input with public OEWS area employment and Census Gazetteer land-area data, validated in Section 4.3.

Net liquid wealth. Liquid financial reserves enable displaced workers to search selectively rather than accept the first available position, financing the time needed to find a well-matched job (Chetty, 2008). Net liquid wealth strips home, business, and vehicle equity from total household net worth:

$$\text{NLW} = \text{THNETWORTH} - \text{THEQ_HOME} - \text{THEQ_BUS} - \text{THEQ_VEH}, \quad (1)$$

where THNETWORTH is total household net worth already net of all liabilities including unsecured debt, and THEQ_HOME, THEQ_BUS, and THEQ_VEH are home, business, and vehicle equity, respectively.

Occupation-level wealth is the WPFINWGT-weighted median pooled across the 2022–2024 SIPP panels (U.S. Census Bureau, 2024c), drawing wealth and the final person weight

from each person-year’s last observed reference month. The component enters the index as $\log(\max(\text{median NLW}, 1))$. Each person-year contributes one observation per unique non-missing occupation code appearing in any of the seven monthly job slots (TJB1_OCC–TJB7_OCC), and carries that person-year’s snapshot wealth and full survey weight into every occupied occupation’s weighted median. Because OEWS tabulates employment by job slot rather than by worker—a person holding two jobs appears once in each occupation (U.S. Bureau of Labor Statistics, 2024b)—assigning a full weight to each job record harmonizes the wealth sample’s occupational composition with the employment counts underlying the transferability and density components.

Growth-weighted skill transferability. Workers whose skills overlap with those demanded by many large, growing occupations face a wider set of reemployment options if displaced (Gathmann and Schönberg, 2010; Nawakitphaitoon and Ormiston, 2016; Eggenberger et al., 2022). Each Modified SIPP occupation receives a 76-element O*NET importance profile drawn from 35 Essential and Transferable Skills and 41 Work Activities importance ratings (U.S. Department of Labor, 2026). Before computing occupational similarity, each feature is converted to an employment-weighted percentile rank across Modified SIPP occupations, assigning tied values the midpoint of the percentile range their combined employment accounts for. Occupational similarity S_{ij} is the cosine similarity between the resulting 76-dimensional percentile vectors. Transferability for origin occupation i is the average of its similarity to every *other* occupation, each destination weighted by its growth-adjusted employment:

$$T_i = \frac{\sum_{j \neq i} E_j (1 + g_j) S_{ij}}{\sum_{j \neq i} E_j (1 + g_j)}, \quad (2)$$

where E_j is May 2024 OEWS national employment (U.S. Bureau of Labor Statistics, 2024b) and g_j is BLS projected employment growth (2024–2034) for destination occupation j (U.S. Bureau of Labor Statistics, 2025). The denominator rescales the weights to sum to one, so T_i is a weighted mean of cosine similarities lying in $[0, 1]$, and occupations whose skills align with large, expanding labor markets receive higher scores. The growth-and-employment weighting follows MA; the one refinement is the exclusion of the origin occupation from its own destination set, addressed next.

The summation in Equation 2 excludes the origin occupation itself ($j \neq i$). MA’s printed formula sums over all j , but the restriction is appropriate on both conceptual and mechanical grounds. Conceptually, transferability measures a worker’s outside options: the occupations to which their skills would carry if displaced from i . The origin is the benchmark against which those options are assessed, not one of the options itself (by assumption, a displaced worker cannot be reemployed in i). Mechanically, the self-similarity term $S_{ii} = 1$ for every occupation and thus carries no cross-sectional information, yet including it would not be harmless: adding it to the weighted average shifts each score upward by $w_i(1 - T_i) / (D + w_i)$, where $w_i = E_i(1 + g_i)$ and $D = \sum_{j \neq i} w_j$. This shift is largest for occupations with high employment and low transferability—such as the clerical and administrative groups at the center of the analysis—which is why the replication excludes $j = i$.

O*NET importance ratings exist only for base .00 occupational categories, meaning that residual “all other” SOC codes and a small number of crosswalk-referenced specializations carry no profiles. For each unprofiled code, importance scores are imputed as a cosine-similarity-weighted average over its $k = 10$ nearest profiled neighbors based on O*NET occupation descriptions. $k = 10$ was chosen by five-fold cross-validation minimizing MAE, and matches the choice in MA. Occupation titles and descriptions are concatenated and embedded with E5-large-v2 (Wang et al., 2022), using the `passage:` prefix. Neighbor weights are cosine similarities shifted to $[0, 2]$, as negative weights would be nonsensical for a similarity-weighted average. Sixty-five of the 388 final-sample occupations contain at least one imputed O*NET child.

Geographic density. Workers in denser, thicker labor markets have access to more alternative employers within commuting distance, reducing expected search durations and widening the set of reemployment options (Bleakley and Lin, 2012; Moretti and Yi, 2024). For each OEWS reporting area a , overall employment density is total area employment divided by land area in square miles. Geographic density for occupation o is the employment-weighted mean of log area density across the areas in which the occupation is observed:

$$G_o = \sum_a \frac{E_{ao}}{E_o^{\text{obs}}} \log\left(\frac{E_a}{A_a}\right), \quad E_o^{\text{obs}} = \sum_a E_{ao}, \quad (3)$$

where E_{ao} is occupation o employment in area a , E_o^{obs} is total observed national employment (sum of non-suppressed area cells), E_o is national employment from the OEWS national estimates file (U.S. Bureau of Labor Statistics, 2024b), E_a is total area employment, and A_a is land area in square miles.

A_a is constructed from the Census 2024 Gazetteer files (U.S. Census Bureau, 2024d), with land area assigned according to the OEWS area code. OEWS areas with 5-digit codes are matched directly to the Census CBSA Gazetteer, whose entries cover metropolitan and micropolitan statistical areas. OEWS nonmetropolitan areas have 7-digit state-prefixed codes and are not separate Census Gazetteer geographies. For these areas, land area is recovered by linking each OEWS nonmetropolitan area to its constituent counties through the BLS area definitions file (U.S. Bureau of Labor Statistics, 2024a) and summing county land areas from the Census county Gazetteer. This produces a land-area measure for all 528 OEWS reporting areas used in the geographic-density formula above.

The component normalizes by E_o^{obs} rather than E_o because some OEWS occupation-area cells are suppressed and absent from the area file. The baseline therefore averages log density across the areas where occupation o is observed, weighting each area by its local employment as a share of E_o^{obs} . Using E_o in the denominator would mechanically lower G_o for occupations with more suppressed employment. The replication uses E_o^{obs} in the baseline and reports the coverage ratio, E_o^{obs}/E_o , as a separate diagnostic (Section 4.3).

Age. Older displaced workers experience substantially larger earnings losses (Couch and Placzek, 2010; Athey et al., 2024) and lower reemployment rates (Farber, 2017) than their younger counterparts. The age component is the ACS-person-weight-adjusted share of workers in each occupation who are aged 55 or older, computed from the 2024 ACS labor-force sample (LABFORCE = 2) (U.S. Census Bureau, 2024a). Because a higher 55-plus share signals a workforce facing greater reemployment barriers, the component enters the composite index with a negative sign.

2.3 Composite Index Construction

Following MA, each component is winsorized at its employment-weighted 1st and 99th percentiles and then converted to an employment-weighted z-score. The baseline composite averages the four

standardized components, with the age component entering negatively:

$$\bar{z}_x^{AC} = \frac{z_x^{wealth} + z_x^{transfer} + z_x^{density} - z_x^{age55+}}{4}. \quad (4)$$

The resulting composite is converted to an employment-weighted exclusive percentile rank, yielding adaptive capacity, $AC_x \in [0, 1)$. Equal weighting of components follows MA and avoids imposing unsupported precision on the relative importance of the four dimensions. Section 4 reports leave-one-component-out sensitivity.

A composite vulnerability score combines AI exposure and the adaptive-capacity deficit:

$$V_x = \sqrt{(1 - AC_x) \times \text{AI exposure}_x}. \quad (5)$$

3 Reproduction of the Original Findings

3.1 Final-Sample Distributions

Table 5 reports the final-sample distributions of AI exposure, the adaptive-capacity index, and its four components. AI exposure averages 0.31 with a long upper tail (median 0.320, max 0.840). Adaptive capacity is an employment-weighted percentile rank, so its mean and quartiles sit near 0.5, 0.25, and 0.75 by construction, while its wide occupational spread (standard deviation 0.290) shows that occupations differ sharply in how well-positioned their workers are to adapt. Component-wise, transferability is tightly concentrated near 0.78, whereas age, log net liquid wealth, and geographic density are far more dispersed. These raw differences in spread reflect differing units, not differing influence, as each component is standardized to mean zero and unit variance before averaging.

Table 5: Descriptive Statistics for AI Exposure and the Adaptive-Capacity Components

	Mean	SD	Min	P25	Median	P75	Max
AI exposure	0.309	0.194	0.000	0.139	0.320	0.451	0.840
Adaptive capacity	0.495	0.290	0.000	0.244	0.499	0.747	0.999
Transferability	0.777	0.059	0.509	0.743	0.783	0.826	0.870
Log net liquid wealth	10.451	1.381	0.000	9.466	10.363	11.552	13.521
Geographic density	5.254	0.279	2.020	5.106	5.221	5.373	7.202
Share aged 55+	0.224	0.079	0.040	0.173	0.222	0.269	0.598

Notes: 388 final-sample occupations. All statistics are employment-weighted, using May 2024 OEWS national employment (U.S. Bureau of Labor Statistics, 2024b); minima and maxima are sample extremes and do not depend on weights. Components are shown on their raw scales, before winsorization and standardization.

3.2 AI Exposure and the Adaptive-Capacity Components

Figure 1 displays the full employment-weighted pairwise structure among vulnerability-score components (AI exposure and the four adaptive-capacity components): employment-weighted distributions on the diagonal, scatter plots with bubble area proportional to employment in the lower triangle, and employment-weighted correlations in the upper triangle. Table 6 reproduces those correlations in numeric form alongside MA’s published values for direct comparison. Net liquid wealth is the strongest single correlate of AI exposure (0.563), followed by geographic density (0.417), transferability (0.239), and the share aged 55 and older (0.184).

The replicated correlations track MA’s closely, with six of the ten distinct pairwise entries falling within 0.02 of their published values. The two largest departures are age-related: the wealth–age correlation is 0.118 against MA’s 0.253, and the transferability–age correlation is 0.179 against 0.092.

Table 6: Pairwise Correlations Among Vulnerability-Score Components

	AI exposure	Transferability	Log wealth	Density	Age 55+
AI exposure	1.000				
Transferability	0.239 (0.227)	1.000			
Log wealth	0.563 (0.591)	0.356 (0.360)	1.000		
Geographic density	0.417 (0.426)	0.138 (0.126)	0.368 (0.355)	1.000	
Age 55+	0.184 (0.152)	0.179 (0.092)	0.118 (0.253)	0.094 (0.108)	1.000

Notes: Employment-weighted correlations across the 388 final-sample occupations. Replication estimates are shown first; MA’s published values (Manning and Aguirre, 2026) are in parentheses.

3.3 The AI Exposure–Adaptive Capacity Relationship

The central finding holds in the replication. The employment-weighted correlation between AI exposure and adaptive capacity is 0.474, 0.028 below MA’s 0.502. The interpretation is identical: occupations with higher measured AI exposure tend to employ workers with greater resources for managing a transition were displacement to occur.

Figure 2 plots AI exposure against adaptive capacity, scales each point by employment, and colors it by the composite vulnerability score from Equation 5. The dashed lines mark the employment-weighted medians of the two axes, so the shaded lower-right quadrant collects occupations that are more exposed than the median worker yet have below-median adaptive capacity. Highly exposed professional occupations, such as software developers (AI exposure 0.45, adaptive capacity 0.97)

and economists (0.46, 0.92), sit in the upper right, pairing high AI exposure with high adaptive capacity, whereas large clerical occupations, such as secretaries and administrative assistants (0.57, 0.14) and cashiers (0.36, 0.15), have similar AI exposure levels but sit near the bottom of the adaptive-capacity distribution.

The top employment-weighted quartile of AI exposure begins at 0.451 and contains 37.29 million workers; of these, 27.85 million (74.7%) are in occupations with above-median adaptive capacity. MA report 37.1 and 26.5 million (71.4%). AI exposure alone, however, flags a large group whose tasks may change but whose workers are comparatively well positioned to absorb a transition. The vulnerable occupations—those above the 75th percentile of AI exposure and below the 25th percentile of adaptive capacity—are the smaller set examined next.

3.4 Vulnerable Occupations

Nine vulnerable occupations employ 5.99 million workers (4.06% of final-sample employment). MA report ten vulnerable occupations employing 6.1 million workers (4.2%). Table 7 lists the replicated group and flags which members also appear in MA’s published list.

Table 7: Replicated and Original Vulnerable Occupations

Occupation	Employment	AI exposure	Adaptive capacity	In MA list
Office clerks, general	2,510,550	0.500	0.230	✓
Secretaries and administrative assistants, except legal, medical, and executive	1,737,820	0.567	0.138	✓
Medical secretaries and administrative assistants	830,760	0.611	0.176	✓
Insurance sales agents	469,480	0.530	0.220	✓
Court, municipal, and license clerks	170,010	0.591	0.119	✓
Payroll and timekeeping clerks	156,950	0.486	0.216	✓
Property appraisers and assessors	59,070	0.518	0.069	✓
Title examiners, abstractors, and searchers	48,170	0.554	0.118	—
Door-to-door sales workers, news and street vendors, and related workers	4,590	0.522	0.227	✓

Notes: Vulnerable occupations rank in the employment-weighted top quartile of AI exposure and the bottom quartile of adaptive capacity. Employment is May 2024 OEWS national employment ([U.S. Bureau of Labor Statistics, 2024b](#)). The final column marks presence in MA’s ten vulnerable occupations ([Manning and Aguirre, 2026](#), Table 7).

The two classifications overlap almost entirely: eight of the nine replicated occupations appear in MA’s list of ten, and the two lists agree on every large clerical category. The one addition is title examiners, abstractors, and searchers, a small occupation of 48,000 workers. The two

MA occupations absent from the replication—eligibility interviewers and tax examiners—are excluded on adaptive-capacity grounds rather than AI exposure, as both clear the exposure threshold comfortably: eligibility interviewers score 0.620 (94th percentile) and tax examiners 0.677 (96th percentile), well above the top-quartile cutoff of 0.451. Eligibility interviewers (156,000 workers) are a marginal case, ranking at the 26th percentile of adaptive capacity (0.263), just above the bottom-quartile threshold of 0.244. Tax examiners (54,000 workers) rank at the 52nd percentile, far from MA’s 18th. The component values of tax examiners are mixed: net liquid wealth at the 60th percentile, transferability at the 37th, geographic density at the 77th, and the share aged 55 and older at the 77th. Because age enters the index with a negative sign, the older workforce subtracts from adaptive capacity ($z = -0.78$) alongside below-average transferability ($z = -0.12$), but above-average geographic density ($z = +0.70$) and wealth ($z = +0.38$) more than offset them, yielding a composite adaptive-capacity z-score of +0.05 and the 52nd-percentile rank.

Three of the four adaptive-capacity components are unlikely to drive the divergence. Age and transferability are built from the same inputs with methodologies near identical to MA’s, leaving little room for the two constructions to part ways; that narrows the candidates to geographic density and wealth, the two components that lift tax examiners above MA’s placement. Wealth, however, can be ruled out, as its median rests on exactly 16 person-years (15 distinct respondents). Any SIPP extraction methodology MA could run draws from this same set, and a single observational difference would not shift the median enough to matter.

That leaves geographic density, the component where the replication substitutes OEWS local employment for MA’s Lightcast employment. OEWS publishes local employment for tax examiners in only 180 of the 528 reporting areas—fewer areas than for 82% of final-sample occupations. The 348 unpublished areas hold 13.5% of the occupation’s national employment, and they are systematically the sparse ones: their median log employment density is 3.71 against 4.84 among published areas, and they include 100 of the 135 nonmetropolitan areas. Because the density measure averages over published areas only (Section 2.2), suppression truncates the low-density tail of this occupation’s geographic distribution and inflates its measured density. The suppression-imputed variant of Section 4.3 assigns each occupation’s unobserved employment the mean log density of its own unpublished areas. Under it, tax examiners’ density falls from 5.44 to 5.18—a z-score of +0.02 against +0.70 at baseline—and their adaptive-capacity rank drops from the 52nd

percentile to the 38th, narrowing but not closing the gap to MA’s 18th.

The mean fill, however, assumes missing employment is distributed evenly across the areas where the occupation has no published cell. If it instead concentrates in the sparsest of those areas, the density inflation is larger than the mean fill corrects. To bound this possibility, the variant is rerun twice, each time with a lower fill. Because each area’s overall density is computed from its published total employment and land area, it is available even where an occupation’s own cell is suppressed, so these fills draw only on observed data: the first uses the 10th percentile of overall log density across the occupation’s unpublished areas, the second the minimum. Tax examiners rank at the 29th percentile of adaptive capacity under the 10th-percentile fill and at the 13th under the minimum. Closing the remaining gap to MA’s 18th therefore requires the unobserved employment of tax examiners to sit near the very bottom of the area-density distribution.

Outside of the tax-examiner discrepancy, the composition of the two vulnerable-worker lists aligns closely. Office and administrative support accounts for 5.41 of the 5.99 million vulnerable workers (90.3%), a concentration that follows directly from the major-group averages. The group has 17.95 million workers and pairs high average AI exposure (0.527, the 85th percentile of the employment-weighted exposure distribution) with low average adaptive capacity (0.353, where adaptive capacity is itself an employment-weighted percentile rank); MA report 17.8 million workers, 0.525, and 0.360 for the same group. The professional groups that face comparable exposure differ instead in their capacity to adjust: business and financial operations occupations average nearly identical AI exposure (0.521, the 85th percentile) but more than double the adaptive capacity (0.774), and computer and mathematical occupations combine average AI exposure of 0.536 (87th percentile) with adaptive capacity of 0.933 (93rd percentile). This pattern reproduces MA’s central finding that what separates the vulnerable occupations from equally exposed non-vulnerable ones is adaptive capacity.

3.5 Geographic Distribution of Vulnerability

Figures 3, 4, and 5 map the replicated area-level distributions of vulnerable-occupation employment share, mean AI exposure, and mean adaptive capacity across 528 OEWS reporting areas. All maps are drawn on the Census Bureau’s 2024 cartographic county boundary files ([U.S. Census Bureau, 2024b](#)), with every county shaded by the value of its OEWS reporting area. MA conduct the

corresponding exercise for 927 metropolitan and micropolitan areas using Lightcast employment and report that vulnerability is geographically diffuse, with the highest shares in college towns and state capitals (Manning and Aguirre, 2026). The maps here provide the open-data counterpart of that geography and extend it to the nonmetropolitan areas that MA’s metropolitan-level analysis does not cover. Figure 6 reports the data quality underlying these maps: the share of each area’s posted OEWS employment accounted for by the 388 final-sample occupations.

4 Robustness Checks and Geographic Validation

The baseline index makes four standard assumptions: equal weights across the four adaptive-capacity components; nearest-neighbor imputation for occupations missing any O*NET child skill rating; a geographic-density formula that normalizes by observed rather than national employment; and a minimum of 15 SIPP observations to form a reliable wealth profile. This section tests whether the correlation between AI exposure and adaptive capacity is robust to modifications in each.

4.1 Leave-One-Component-Out Sensitivity

Table 8 rebuilds the adaptive-capacity index in Equation 4 after dropping one component at a time, re-summing the signed z-scores of the remaining components and re-ranking by employment. For each specification, it reports the correlation between AI exposure and adaptive capacity and the vulnerable worker employment share, alongside MA’s values for the same exercise. The correlation stays positive in every specification, and, more tellingly, the whole sensitivity profile tracks MA’s: dropping wealth lowers r to 0.308 (MA: 0.29), dropping density to 0.362 (0.38), dropping transferability to 0.443 (0.50), and dropping the age share raises it to 0.574 (0.58). Wealth is the single most important component—its removal cuts the correlation by a third—consistent with its being the strongest individual correlate of AI exposure. Removing geographic density reduces the correlation by 24% (0.474 to 0.362), almost exactly the 24% decline MA report for their Lightcast-based density (0.502 to 0.38); the public substitute therefore carries the same marginal information as the proprietary input. Age behaves as expected in both studies: because older-worker shares are themselves positively correlated with AI exposure yet enter adaptive capacity with a negative sign, removing age strengthens the correlation between AI exposure and adaptive capacity.

The vulnerable-worker share moves in the same directions as MA’s. Dropping wealth raises the share (to 4.7%, against MA’s 8.0%), dropping density lowers it (to 2.6%, against MA’s 5.4%), dropping transferability lowers it (to 2.0%, against MA’s 3.1%), and dropping age nearly eliminates it (0.2%, matching MA exactly).

Table 8: Leave-One-Component-Out Robustness

Specification	Correlation (r)		Vulnerable share	
	MA	Replication	MA	Replication
Baseline, all four components	0.502	0.474	4.2%	4.1%
Drop net liquid wealth	0.29	0.308	8.0%	4.7%
Drop geographic density	0.38	0.362	5.4%	2.6%
Drop transferability	0.50	0.443	3.1%	2.0%
Drop age 55+	0.58	0.574	0.2%	0.2%

Notes: Each specification rebuilds the mean z-score and employment-weighted percentile rank after removing the indicated component, using the full 388-occupation sample. r denotes the employment-weighted correlation between AI exposure and the rebuilt adaptive-capacity index; the vulnerable share is the share of final-sample employment in vulnerable occupations. MA values are from Manning and Aguirre (2026), Table 11, which reports non-baseline correlations to two decimals.

4.2 Sample-Restriction Robustness

Table 9 restricts the sample and rebuilds the adaptive-capacity index from scratch within each subset.¹ The weighted correlation with AI exposure is then recomputed, so each restricted sample is ranked against itself rather than against the full sample.

Excluding the 65 occupations with any imputed O*NET child reduces the sample to 323 occupations and lowers the correlation from 0.474 to 0.422. Requiring that at least 50% of local OEWS employment be directly observed retains 379 occupations and barely increases the correlation to 0.475. Tightening that threshold to 75% observed coverage reduces the sample to 338 occupations and raises the correlation slightly to 0.482. Raising the SIPP observation minimum from 15 to 30 trims the sample to 310 occupations and increases the correlation to 0.496. Raising it further to 50 observations reduces the sample to 219 occupations and increases the correlation to 0.527.

¹Each component is re-winsorized at the subset’s employment-weighted 1st and 99th percentiles and re-standardized to an employment-weighted z-score, and the re-averaged composite is re-ranked into employment-weighted percentiles over the retained occupations.

Table 9: Sample-Restriction Robustness

Restriction	Occupations	Employment (M)	Correlation (r)
Baseline (final sample)	388	147.44	0.474
Exclude occupations with imputed O*NET child	323	124.14	0.422
Require local OEWS coverage $\geq 50\%$	379	147.23	0.475
Require local OEWS coverage $\geq 75\%$	338	143.48	0.482
Require at least 30 SIPP observations	310	141.68	0.496
Require at least 50 SIPP observations	219	130.69	0.527

Notes: Each row restricts the sample and rebuilds the adaptive-capacity index on the retained occupations, so each subsample is ranked against itself. r denotes the employment-weighted correlation between AI exposure and the rebuilt index; M denotes millions of workers.

4.3 Validation of the Public Geographic-Density Measure

Four checks validate the OEWS-based geographic-density measure as a replacement for MA’s proprietary Lightcast input: agreement with published correlation benchmarks, national occupational coverage, suppression incidence, and normalization sensitivity.

The OEWS-based density closely tracks MA’s published correlations. Its employment-weighted correlation with AI exposure is 0.417, against 0.426 for MA’s Lightcast measure. Correlations with the other three adaptive-capacity components are equally close, each within 0.02 of MA’s published value: transferability, 0.138 against 0.126; net liquid wealth, 0.368 against 0.355; and the share aged 55 and older, 0.094 against 0.108 (the density row of Table 6).

Occupational coverage is high, and its gaps follow a predictable pattern. Across the 388 final-sample occupations, the median occupation has 0.92 of its national employment observed in OEWS area files and the employment-weighted mean coverage is 0.95; only nine occupations fall below 0.50, and every one employs fewer workers than the median occupation. This pattern is expected, since rarer occupations are the ones most often suppressed in any given area. When binning the full set of occupations for which density is constructed into national-employment deciles, mean coverage rises monotonically from 0.53 in the smallest decile to 0.96 in the largest (Table 10); Figure 7 shows the same gradient across the final sample, plotting each occupation’s coverage against its national employment. Excluding occupations below 50% or 75% coverage leaves the AI exposure–adaptive-capacity correlation essentially unchanged (Table 9).

Table 10: OEWS Local Employment Coverage by National-Employment Decile

Decile	Employment range	N	Mean coverage
1	1,390–18,940	52	0.53
2	19,500–32,100	52	0.67
3	32,210–49,910	52	0.73
4	50,330–72,190	52	0.81
5	72,500–100,870	52	0.86
6	101,140–151,130	52	0.89
7	151,750–215,520	52	0.92
8	219,010–348,330	52	0.93
9	348,630–727,070	52	0.95
10	742,580–3,988,140	52	0.96

Notes: Deciles bin the 520 occupations for which geographic density is constructed (52 per decile) by May 2024 OEWS national employment (U.S. Bureau of Labor Statistics, 2024b); the employment range reports each decile’s smallest and largest occupation. Coverage is the share of an occupation’s national employment that appears in the May 2024 OEWS area files (U.S. Bureau of Labor Statistics, 2024b) rather than being suppressed. Mean coverage is the unweighted mean across the 52 occupations in each decile.

Cell-level suppression is light and not concentrated by geography. Only 2.0% of the 186,463 detailed occupation-area cells are suppressed, and the average per-area suppression rate is nearly identical in CBSA (1.7%) and nonmetropolitan (1.7%) areas (Table 11).

Table 11: OEWS Cell-Suppression Incidence by Area Type

Area type	N areas	Mean rate	Median rate	Total cells	Suppressed cells
CBSA	393	1.7%	1.2%	141,164	2,966
Nonmetropolitan	135	1.7%	1.4%	45,299	785
All	528	1.7%	1.3%	186,463	3,751

Notes: Each cell is a detailed-occupation \times area pair in the May 2024 OEWS area files (U.S. Bureau of Labor Statistics, 2024b); a cell is suppressed when `tot_emp` is reported as “***”. Mean and median suppression rates are unweighted averages across areas; employment weighting is infeasible because suppressed cells have no `tot_emp` value.

Normalizing by observed employment E_o^{obs} rather than national employment E_o when aggregating cell-level densities is the substantively correct choice. The geographic density component is a weighted average of log employment-to-land-area ratios, and the observed-employment normalization in Equation 3 ensures those weights sum to one. Substituting OEWS national employment in the denominator instead makes the weights sum to each occupation’s coverage ratio, an approach that confounds labor-market density with suppression intensity. For example, an occupation concentrated in a few dense metros but with many suppressed OEWS cells appears artificially sparse under this alternative, not because workers are geographically dispersed but because the data are in-

complete. The coverage-deflated measure collapses the density–AI exposure correlation from 0.417 to 0.055 and drags the AI exposure–adaptive-capacity correlation from 0.474 to 0.349 (Table 12). A third specification is imputation, where each occupation’s unobserved employment share is assigned the mean log employment density of the areas in which that occupation has no published cell. This specification leaves the AI exposure–adaptive-capacity correlation nearly unchanged, moving it from 0.474 to 0.467, while the density–AI exposure correlation declines moderately, from 0.417 to 0.378 (Table 12). However, the allocation assumption—that an occupation’s unobserved employment is spread across its unpublished areas at their average density—cannot be verified. The assumption also binds hardest exactly where coverage is worst: railroad conductors, with 9.6% coverage, swing from the 94th to the 9th adaptive-capacity percentile. OEWS publishes their employment in only four unusually dense areas, so the imputation assigns the other 90.4% of their employment—suppressed everywhere else they work—the far sparser average density of the remaining areas. The observed-employment normalization is therefore a better proxy for MA’s proprietary geographic input than either alternative: its 0.417 density–AI exposure correlation nearly matches MA’s 0.426, against 0.055 deflated and 0.378 imputed, and its 0.474 adaptive-capacity correlation is closest to MA’s 0.502 (Manning and Aguirre, 2026).

Table 12: Sensitivity to the Treatment of Employment in Suppressed OEWS Cells

Density denominator	$r(\text{density, AI exposure})$	$r(\text{AI exposure, adaptive capacity})$
E_o^{obs} (baseline)	0.417	0.474
E_o (coverage-deflated)	0.055	0.349
E_o (suppression-imputed)	0.378	0.467

Notes: Employment-weighted correlations across the 388 final-sample occupations. E_o^{obs} is total employment summed across non-suppressed area cells in the May 2024 OEWS area files (U.S. Bureau of Labor Statistics, 2024b); E_o is national employment from the OEWS national estimates file (U.S. Bureau of Labor Statistics, 2024b). The suppression-imputed specification assigns each occupation’s unobserved employment share the mean log employment density of the areas in which the occupation has no published cell. The published MA benchmark (Lightcast density) yields correlations of 0.426 and 0.502 (Manning and Aguirre, 2026).

5 Conclusion

This paper set out to test whether the central findings of Manning and Aguirre (2026) survive independent replication from public data, and whether their one proprietary input—Lightcast geographic employment—is necessary to recover those findings. The exercise reconstructs the adaptive-

capacity index from the same conceptual design, imports the identical published AI-exposure scores (Eloundou et al., 2024b), and substitutes public OEWS area employment (U.S. Bureau of Labor Statistics, 2024b) and Census Gazetteer land area (U.S. Census Bureau, 2024d) for the proprietary geographic measure. On balance, the original study’s principal results are confirmed.

Four key findings of the original study are reproduced. First, the positive association between AI exposure and adaptive capacity holds: the employment-weighted correlation is 0.474, against MA’s 0.502, and it remains positive across every leave-one-component-out and sample-restriction specification (Tables 8 and 9). Second, the vulnerable group is small and concentrated: nine occupations employing 6.0 million workers (4.1% of covered employment), against MA’s ten occupations and 6.1 million (4.2%), with eight of the nine occupations common to both lists and office and administrative support accounting for roughly 90% of vulnerable employment (Table 7). Third, the conclusion that vulnerability is driven by low adaptive capacity rather than high exposure alone is confirmed: business, financial, and computational occupations are as exposed as the clerical group yet sit far higher in adaptive capacity. Fourth, the component-level correlation structure aligns closely, with six of ten pairwise correlations within 0.02 of MA’s published values (Table 6).

The replication also confirms that the proprietary geographic input is not necessary. The public OEWS-and-Gazetteer density correlates 0.417 with AI exposure against MA’s 0.426 for Lightcast, matches MA’s published correlations with the other three components to within 0.02, and carries virtually the same marginal information, as removing it lowers the AI exposure–adaptive-capacity correlation by 24% in both studies.

Two results are not reproduced and remain unresolved. First, occupation counts after the minimum-SIPP-observation filter do not match MA’s even under MA’s own rule of counting unique SIPP respondents: the replication retains 386 occupations covering 148.7 million workers, while MA report 369 occupations covering 149.9 million—367 occupations net of two codes that carry no OEWS employment (Section 2.1). Fewer occupations covering more workers implies that different occupations are passing the threshold, so the gap reflects an undocumented choice in how MA’s SIPP wealth extraction assigns occupations to respondents, not a difference in threshold strictness (Tables 3 and 4). Second, tax examiners are classified as vulnerable in MA but not in the replication. The adaptive-capacity percentile of tax examiners is 52nd in this replication against MA’s 18th. The gap primarily traces to OEWS suppression, which withholds the occupation’s sparsest 348 reporting

areas and thereby inflates its measured geographic density. Correcting for the suppression narrows the gap, but closing it entirely requires assuming the withheld employment sits at the very bottom of the area-density distribution, so the discrepancy remains ultimately unresolved (Section 3.4).

In sum, the evidence indicates that the substantive conclusions of Manning and Aguirre (2026)—a positive AI exposure–adaptive capacity gradient, a small and clerically concentrated vulnerable group, and the primacy of adaptive capacity in determining vulnerability—are robust, reproducible without access to the original code, and recoverable entirely from public data.

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Component Pairwise Matrix

Figure 1: Pairwise structure of AI exposure and the four adaptive-capacity components across the 388 final-sample occupations. Diagonal panels show the employment-weighted distribution of each measure; lower-triangle panels are scatter plots with point area proportional to May 2024 OEWS national employment (U.S. Bureau of Labor Statistics, 2024b); upper-triangle panels report employment-weighted correlations.

Figure 2: AI exposure and adaptive capacity across the 388 final-sample occupations. Point area is proportional to May 2024 OEWS national employment ([U.S. Bureau of Labor Statistics, 2024b](#)), and color reports the composite vulnerability score in Equation 5. Dashed lines mark the employment-weighted median of each axis.

Vulnerable-Occupation Employment Share by County

Counties shaded by their OEWS reporting-area value (uniform within each area)

Figure 3: Vulnerable-occupation employment share by OEWS reporting area: the share of each area's posted May 2024 OEWS employment ([U.S. Bureau of Labor Statistics, 2024b](#)) held by the nine vulnerable occupations of Table 7. Each county is shaded with the value of its OEWS reporting area, with counties assigned to areas through the BLS area definitions file ([U.S. Bureau of Labor Statistics, 2024a](#)), and the boundaries of the 528 reporting areas are overlaid. County geometries are from the Census 2024 cartographic boundary files ([U.S. Census Bureau, 2024b](#)).

Employment-Weighted AI Exposure by County

Counties shaded by their OEWS reporting-area value (uniform within each area)

Figure 4: Mean AI exposure by OEWS reporting area: the mean of AI exposure across the final-sample occupations observed in each area, weighted by May 2024 OEWS area employment (U.S. Bureau of Labor Statistics, 2024b). Each county is shaded with the value of its OEWS reporting area, with counties assigned to areas through the BLS area definitions file (U.S. Bureau of Labor Statistics, 2024a), and the boundaries of the 528 reporting areas are overlaid. County geometries are from the Census 2024 cartographic boundary files (U.S. Census Bureau, 2024b).

Employment-Weighted Adaptive Capacity by County

Counties shaded by their OEWS reporting-area value (uniform within each area)

Figure 5: Mean adaptive capacity by OEWS reporting area: the mean of adaptive capacity across the final-sample occupations observed in each area, weighted by May 2024 OEWS area employment (U.S. Bureau of Labor Statistics, 2024b). Each county is shaded with the value of its OEWS reporting area, with counties assigned to areas through the BLS area definitions file (U.S. Bureau of Labor Statistics, 2024a), and the boundaries of the 528 reporting areas are overlaid. County geometries are from the Census 2024 cartographic boundary files (U.S. Census Bureau, 2024b).

Final-Sample Employment Coverage by County

Counties shaded by their OEWS reporting-area value (uniform within each area)

Figure 6: Final-sample employment coverage by OEWS reporting area: the share of each area's posted May 2024 OEWS employment ([U.S. Bureau of Labor Statistics, 2024b](#)) accounted for by the 388 final-sample occupations. Each county is shaded with the value of its OEWS reporting area, with counties assigned to areas through the BLS area definitions file ([U.S. Bureau of Labor Statistics, 2024a](#)), and the boundaries of the 528 reporting areas are overlaid. County geometries are from the Census 2024 cartographic boundary files ([U.S. Census Bureau, 2024b](#)).

Figure 7: Local OEWS employment coverage by occupation. Each point is one of the 388 final-sample occupations. The vertical axis is coverage: the share of the occupation’s May 2024 OEWS national employment (U.S. Bureau of Labor Statistics, 2024b) that appears in the OEWS area files rather than being suppressed. The horizontal axis is May 2024 OEWS national employment (U.S. Bureau of Labor Statistics, 2024b) (log scale).